

POSSIBLE ANTAMOEBCIC AGENTS. PART XI. SYNTHESIS OF
COMPOUNDS ANALOGOUS TO ENTAMIDE

BY A. B. SEN AND O. P. MADAM

Several substituted dichloroacetanilides have been synthesised from substituted *N*-alkylanilines with a view to testing them for their antamoebic activity.

Recently Boots Pure Drug Co. have introduced a new synthetic amoebicide, Entamide (2:2-dichloro-4'-hydroxy-*N*-methylacetanilide). Its action on *E. histolytica* is specific; it is non-toxic, inexpensive and the treatment with it is convenient as no bed rest is required. Bristow *et al.* (*Trans. Roy. Soc. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1956, 50, 182) and Woodruff (*Brit. Med. J.*, 1956, 1, 288, described it to be very useful for such patients who were symptomless cyst passers.

The present work reports the synthesis of eleven substituted dichloroacetanilides (II) from the corresponding *N*-alkylanilines having different substituents (hydroxy, methoxy, chloro, iodo and methyl) in the nucleus and different alkyl radicals (ethyl, propylⁿ and butylⁿ) at the nitrogen atom, with a view to studying their antamoebic activity.

(I)

(Entamide)

(II)

{ R' and R'' = substituents in the nucleus.
R = substituent at nitrogen atom.

3-Chloro-4-hydroxy-*N*-alkylanilines were prepared by refluxing 2-chloro-4-aminophenol and different alkyl halides in absolute alcohol in the presence of calcined potassium carbonate. 3-Chloro-4-methoxy-*N*-alkylanilines were obtained by the reductive alkylation of 2-chloro-4-nitroanisole, following the method of Emerson and Mohrman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 69) using acetaldehyde, acetone and butyrⁿaldehyde. 2-Methyl-4-iodo-*N*-alkylanilines were obtained similarly from 2-methyl-4-iodoaniline, acetone and butyrⁿaldehyde.

Dichloroacetanilides have been synthesised from 3-chloro-4-hydroxy-, 3-chloro-4-methoxy- and 2-methyl-4-iodo-anilines, 3-chloro-4-hydroxy- and 3-chloro-4-methoxy- and 2-methyl-4-iodo-*N*-alkylanilines by the action of dichloroacetyl chloride (in dichloroethane) following the method of Surrey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2216).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

3-Chloro-4-hydroxy-N-alkylanilines.—The starting material for this was 2-chloro-4-nitrophenol which was prepared from *p*-nitrophenol according to Christiansen (*ibid.*, 1923, 45, 2192). This was easily reduced to *o*-chloro-*p*-aminophenol with sodium hydrosulphite. (Reduction with zinc dust and NaOH or Fe and HCl was not found to be satisfactory). Attempts made for the synthesis of *o*-chloro-*p*-methylaminophenol and its sulphate (cf. Christiansen, *loc. cit.*) did not succeed. Hence, a large number of other methods were tried for the *N*-alkylation of *o*-chloro-*p*-aminophenol, most of which were unsuccessful.

Finally 2-chloro-4-*N*-ethylamino-, -propyl^lamino- and -butylⁿamino-phenols were obtained by refluxing 2-chloro-4-aminophenol with appropriate alkyl bromide or iodide accompanied with calcined potassium carbonate for 8 to 12 hours.

2-Chloro-4-*N*-ethylaminophenol.—*o*-Chloro-*p*-aminophenol (4.3 g., 0.03 *M*), ethyl iodide (4.7 g., 0.03 *M*) and calcined potassium carbonate (2.1 g., 0.015 *M*) were refluxed in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) for 8 hours on a water-bath. Potassium iodide formed was filtered off, alcohol removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken up in ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and finally the ether was removed. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure when the phenol was obtained as a liquid, b.p. 172°/16 mm, which soon solidified and yielded a compound of m.p. 63-64°, yield 2.6 g. (51%). (Found: C, 53.76; H, 5.44; N, 7.92. C₈H₁₀ONCl requires C, 55.97; H, 5.83; N, 8.16%).

2-Chloro-4-*N*-propyl^laminophenol.—*o*-Chloro-*p*-aminophenol (0.03 *M*), propyl^l iodide (0.03 *M*) and calcined K₂CO₃ (0.015 *M*) were heated in absolute alcohol for 10 hours. 2-Chloro-4-*N*-propyl^laminophenol was obtained in the usual way, m.p. 107°, yield 50% of the theory. (Found: N, 7.39. C₉H₁₂ONCl requires N, 7.54%).

2-Chloro-4-*N*-butylⁿaminophenol was obtained in the same way by refluxing *o*-chloro-*p*-aminophenol (4.3 g., 0.03 *M*) and butylⁿ bromide (4.1 g., 0.03 *M*) in absolute alcohol for 12 hours; b.p. 208°/6 mm, yield 3.0 g. (53%). (Found: N, 6.85. C₁₀H₁₄ONCl requires N, 7.01%).

3-Chloro-4-methoxy-N-alkylanilines.—*o*-Chloro-*p*-nitroanisole was prepared from *o*-chloro-*p*-nitrophenol, following the method of Hodgson and Handlay (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 543). 2-Chloro-4-*N*-ethylamino-, -propyl^lamino- and -butylⁿamino-anisoles were obtained from *o*-chloro-*p*-nitroanisole, following the method of Emerson and Mohrman (*loc. cit.*).

2-Chloro-4-*N*-butylⁿaminoanisole.—*o*-Chloro-*p*-nitroanisole (3.75 g., 0.02 *M*), butyrⁿ-aldehyde (5.16 g., 0.06 *M*), sodium acetate (0.4 g.) and absolute alcohol (35 c.c.) were refluxed for 1 hour. The mixture was then reduced catalytically using Raney nickel till no more of hydrogen was absorbed. On releasing the pressure, the mixture was removed from hydrogenation bottle. Raney nickel was filtered off and 2-chloro-4-*N*-

butylⁿ-aminoanisole was obtained in the usual way as a yellow liquid, b.p. 188°/5 mm, yield 5.8 g. (75%). (Found: N, 6.50. C₁₁H₁₆ONCl requires N, 6.55%).

2-Chloro-4-N-ethylaminoanisole.—*o*-Chloro-*p*-nitroanisole (2.34 g., 0.0125 M), acetaldehyde (5.5 g., 0.0125 M) and sodium acetate (0.2 g.) in absolute alcohol were directly reduced catalytically. The anisole was obtained in the usual way as a thick red liquid, b.p. 165°/5 mm, yield 2.1 g. (77%). (Found: N, 7.76. C₉H₁₁ONCl requires N, 7.74%).

2-Chloro-4-N-propylaminoanisole was obtained similarly from *o*-chloro-*p*-nitroanisole (3.75 g., 0.02 M), acetone (4.64 g., 0.08 M) and sodium acetate (0.2 g.) as a brownish yellow liquid, b.p. 132°/5 mm, yield 2.6 g. (54%). (Found: N, 6.82. C₁₀H₁₄ONCl requires N, 7.01%).

The *picrate* was prepared in absolute alcohol in the usual way, m.p. 172°. (Found: N, 13.01. C₁₆H₁₇O₈N₄Cl requires N, 13.06%).

2-Methyl-4-iodo-N-alkylanilines.—*2-Methyl-4-iodo-N-propylaniline* and *2-methyl-4-iodo-N-butylaniline* were prepared from 5-iodo-2-aminotoluene by the method of Emerson and Mohrman (*loc. cit.*).

2-Methyl-4-iodo-N-propylaniline.—5-Iodo-2-aminotoluene (4.78 g., 0.02 M), dry acetone (4.64 g., 0.08 M), sodium acetate (0.4 g.) and absolute alcohol were heated on a water-bath for 1 hour and then reduced catalytically. The aniline derivative was obtained as a yellow liquid, b.p. 122°/6 mm, yield 2.7 g. (47%). (Found: N, 5.18. C₁₀H₁₄NI requires N, 5.09%).

2-Methyl-4-iodo-N-butylaniline was obtained similarly from 5-iodo-2-aminotoluene (2.33 g., 0.01 M) and butyrⁿaldehyde (1.44 g., 0.02 M) with sodium acetate and absolute alcohol as a light yellow liquid, b.p. 135-36°/5 mm, yield 1.0 g. (35%). (Found: N, 4.51. C₁₁H₁₆NI requires N, 4.87%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way in alcohol, m.p. 146°. (Found: N, 10.27. C₁₇H₁₉O₇N₄I requires N, 10.81%).

Dichloroacetanilides were prepared from 3-chloro-4-hydroxyaniline, 3-chloro-4-methoxyaniline, 2-methyl-4-iodoaniline and from the corresponding *N*-alkylanilines mentioned above, following the method of Surrey (*loc. cit.*). Dichloroacetyl chloride (0.005 M) in dichloroethane (5 c.c.) was added gradually with stirring to a mixture of substituted aniline (0.005 M) in dichloroethane (15 c.c.) and 1*N*-NaOH (5 c.c.). The temperature was kept between 0° and -5° by external cooling. The reaction mixture was stirred and was kept at room temperature overnight. Organic layer was separated, washed successively with 1 *N*-NaOH, water, 1 *N*-HCl and water. The dichloroethane extract was then dried over K₂CO₃ (calcined). The dichloroacetanilides were obtained after removing dichloroethane and were recrystallised from suitable solvents as required or purified by distilling under reduced pressure.

The m.p., b.p., yield, analysis etc. of dichloroacetanilides are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	M.P. or B.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
R' & R'' = 3-chloro-4-hydroxy.					
H	133°	88%	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ NCl ₃	5.35	5.50
Et	176°	23	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl ₃	4.90	4.95
Pr ^t	175°/5 mm	45	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₃	4.38	4.72
Bu ⁿ	129°/5	47	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl ₃	4.69	4.50
R' & R'' = 3-chloro-4-methoxy.					
H	124°	75	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ NCl ₃	5.03	5.21
Et	105°/5	46	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ NCl ₃	4.63	4.72
Pr ^t	113°	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl ₃	4.38	4.50
Bu ⁿ	133°/5	50	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl ₃	4.20	4.31
R' & R'' = 2-methyl-4-iodo.					
H	190°	79	C ₉ H ₉ ONCl ₂ I	4.05	4.07
Pr ^t	134°	78	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ONCl ₂ I	3.89	3.62
Bu ⁿ	61°	51	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ONCl ₂ I	3.39	3.50

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCENOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCENOW.

Received October 5, 1955